

OPEN, USEFUL AND REUSABLE DATA (OURData) POLICY IMPACT ON STARTUP INNOVATION

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The OURdata index benchmarks the design and implementation of open data policies at the central level and stresses the sustained political and policy relevance of this areas of work for OECD member and partner countries and beyond,. Open Government data creates social and business values and are a core component of strategies aimed at strengthening good governance (OECD, 2022), and they have a significant potential for business applications (WB, 2021) However, it may be possible that some obstacles are preventing the full benefit of open government data in terms of innovation, and in this paper we aim to study these obstacles and, possibly, catalysts for better usage of open data in startup innovation.

Open data index is based on three pillars: open data availability, accessibility and government support for data reuse. Six dimensions of Digital Government are government as a platform, open by default, data-driven public sector, digital by design, user driven and proactive. The index is based on the analytical framework for open data policies, namely OECD Working Paper Open Government Data: Towards Empirical Analysis of Open Government Data Initiatives (Ubaldi, 2013) which led to current OECD index in 2017 and 2019. It can be shown that just publishing open data does not automatically yield economic positive effects, which was also evident in Croatia, but accessibility and also networking is equally important. Also, Croatian startups lack an actual eco-system in areas such as AI, so a lot of risk is involved in making such business ideas work. EU projects and funds may be of some help, but not if the competitions are organized on the basis of the ‘fastest finger’, i.e., only the speed of submitting an application is a criterion for winning the tender,. However, recently we have seen many successful Croatian startups appear, so they must have been able to overcome the aforementioned problems. The question remains how much open data contributed to the success of Croatian startups. Business areas that appear as alluring are tourism, food, construction and health, but also transport and sustainability. In the area of transport and sustainability open government data may be of some importance. For investment into construction, availability of government data concerning ownership of properties may also play an important role for new startups.

In this paper we analyze how Croatian open data policies have impacted startups and we try to find concrete examples of startups that have benefited from those policies, we enumerate and analyze those policies and compare them to similar policies in EU countries, in order to draw conclusions about their efficiency and effectiveness.

Open government data promotes transparency, accountability and value creation. This last aspect is of particular interest when researching startups and innovation, but transparency and accountability are equally important for a successful and functional open data ecosystem. This ecosystem in Croatia is determined by e-government strategy and decision to make data open by design. However, OECD countries have become aware that formal government open data requirements are essential, but not sufficient, which may even give rise to “open washing” and the accessibility may be even more important than availability of open data, as availability does not always result in implementation and availability is more important than quantity of open data (Ubaldi, 2013), which may turn to be a problem to achieve in case of Croatia and other countries that are less successful than the leaders in open data, namely Korea, Canada, France, Ireland, Japan, as political culture and administrative structure (multi-level) may be reason for slowing down, and governments should also monitor and promote re-use and monitor economic and social impact of open data in order to determine better policies. (OECD Open Data Index, 2022).

It has been determined that Open data play a role in startup innovation and entrepreneurial activity (Hubert et al., 2022). In our case we are interested in value creation in the economic sense, and for that we must determine the quality of Croatian startup ecosystem, and see if it can also be linked to open data policies. Luckily, there is such an index, and on this index the leading countries are USA, UK and Israel. Croatia has recently dropped 9 places and is now 45th and 9th in the SEE region (Global Startup Ecosystem Index, 2022). A comparable country is Slovenia, which is similarly positioned on the 47th and 11th place and may serve as a benchmark, although most startups in Slovenia are in foodtech and transportation, whereas in Croatia it is leisure (hotels etc.), green tech and energy, as well as IoT (sensors) (GSEI, StartubBlink). Data accessibility is crucial for startup companies, as they have to collect good data first in order to implement data-driven approach. It becomes clear that one of main startups for which open data are crucial is Rimac Automobiles, Ltd., because it makes electric cars that depend on geospatial data, which are provided by government agencies, notably Shared Service Center (SSC), in making, and the Croatian Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets.. In fact, it can be seen that Croatian e-government strategy has played an important role in leading up to this development in the past 10 years (Vračić, 2014), and those startups in Croatia did not appear out of the blue, as it can result in better entrepreneurial strategies (Kitsios et al., 2018). In fact, the type of country determines competitive advantage (Porter, 1998) and in this case Croatian strategies assisted by EU funds have played into this hand by enabling the right kind of development (Saberli et al., 2019), leading to the innovation in electric cars, sports cars in nature (which is naturally linked to leisure as a specific feature of Croatia, another is also roads, love for sports, etc.) and in the future also autonomous cars, SAE level 5 (without drivers). Of course, many startups did in fact come out of the blue or by the efforts of their makers, such as Bellabeat or Infobip, but the overall climate for startups has improved due to the development of e-government and abolishing of outdated practices (seals, etc.), while introducing e-citizens and other modern features of information society. The next step in the SSC project that was started in December 2019, would be to actually monitor economic impact in the Ministry of Economy in order to determine better ways to support businesses. The role of the EU as a funding and regulatory force is also of primary importance, although the non EU countries are leaders in startup innovation (US, UK and Israel), but France and Germany are not too far behind.

In this paper we were able to prove that open government data can indeed play an important role in startup innovation, and a rather straightforward example of Rimac Automobiles Ltd. can serve as a good epitome of such a link, implying causality. However, there is much left to be desired in terms of using open government data for startup innovation, as well in terms of accessibility of such data, which are not exploited to the full extent or presented in a suitable manner for startups to be able to profit from them or get a great business idea. Many Croatian startups are in fact directed towards households and citizens, as consultancies that explain how they can better analyse their own data in order to improve their daily functioning, e.g. in terms of energy saving, driving around and parking more efficiently, saving unused food, disposing garbage, etc.

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